

VERIFICATION OF A MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING FLOW MODEL

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ABSTRACT

A science based multi-dimensional model of the resin transfer molding (RTM) process has been developed which can be used to simulate the infiltration of resin into a fibrous preform. Frequency dependent electromagnetic sensing (FDEMS) has been developed for in-situ monitoring of the RTM process. Flow visualization tests conducted in a transparent mold with oil and E-glass fabric preforms showed that FDEMS can accurately detect the position of the resin flow front during mold filling, and that the model-predicted flow front patterns agreed well with the measured flow front patterns. Mold filling experiments conducted with a reactive epoxy resin and carbon fabric preforms have shown good agreement between model predicted and sensor-measured infiltration patterns.

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) is a cost-effective method of fabricating primary aircraft structures. It enables the use of a variety of automated textile processes for making the dry fiber preforms, several of which offer through-the-thickness reinforcement. RTM has been used for decades in various industries for less critical structures having low fiber volumes and readily processed resins. The challenge in adapting RTM to primary aircraft structures lies in ensuring successful infiltration and cure for high fiber volumes, limited resin processing windows and geometrically complex shapes.

A joint research program between NASA Langley Research Center, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University and the College of William and Mary is underway to develop a science-based

understanding of the RTM process in order to minimize costly trial-and-error steps during process development of a structure, and to ensure quality during production. This involves characterizing the processing behavior of the fibers and resins, developing mathematical models of the RTM process, and monitoring significant process variables in real time. The ultimate goals of this program are to develop a comprehensive three-dimensional RTM model for complex shapes and fiber architectures, and to incorporate the model into an intelligent process control system which uses frequency dependent electromagnetic sensing (FDEMS) for sensing the process variables in real time.

In this paper, experimental and analytical techniques that are being used in the development of a comprehensive, multi-dimensional RTM simulation model will be discussed. Specifically, flow visualization experiments were performed to verify the flow front and infiltration-time predictions of the resin infiltration submodel, to verify the permeability versus compaction measurements obtained from preform characterization experiments, and to demonstrate the ability of FDEMS sensing to detect the position of the flow front. Also, the results of mold filling experiments conducted with a reactive epoxy resin and carbon fabric preforms will be presented. The metallic mold has an array of six FDEMS sensors embedded in the base plate to monitor resin infiltration and cure.

RESIN INFILTRATION MODEL

The resin infiltration model was developed to determine the position of the flow front and the pressure distribution inside the preform. In development of the flow model the following assumptions are made: 1) the textile preform is a porous medium, 2) the preform permeability is heterogeneous and anisotropic; and 3) the resin is incompressible, and capillary and inertia effects are neglected (low Reynolds number flow).

The macroscopic resin flow model is based on Darcy's Law which is used to describe the flow through porous media. The momentum equation is replaced by Darcy's Law which relates the flow rate to the pressure gradient. Darcy's Law can be written as

$$\vec{q} = -\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla \cdot P \quad (1)$$

The continuity equation for an incompressible flow can be written as

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{q} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Combining Darcy's Law and the continuity equation the general expression governing the resin infiltration into a textile preform is

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla \cdot P \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

The solution of this equation gives the pressure distribution within the region of the textile preform where the resin has saturated the preform.

Many methods of modeling free boundary movement have been explored over the past decade [1]. The finite element/control volume technique was used in this investigation to simulate the resin front movement. A complete description of the model development is available in [2].

EXPERIMENTAL

The major components of the flow visualization apparatus are shown in Fig. 1. They include the visualization fixture, the video camera and high resolution tape recorder, and the compressed air pressurized resin pot. Resin injection pressure was controlled by an air pressure regulator mounted on the resin pot. Pressure was monitored during the experiment with gages installed at the exit of the resin pot and at the visualization fixture resin inlet ports.

The fixture consisted of a square aluminum frame with a 3.8 cm thick poly(methylmethacrylate) top plate. The dimensions of the test cavity are 0.61m x 0.61m. A total of nine FDEMS sensors were mounted in the aluminum bottom plate of the mold. The locations of the sensors in the bottom plate are shown in Fig. 2. The FDEMS sensors were installed into the aluminum mounting plugs and the mounting plugs were inserted into the cavities that were machined into the bottom plate. Details regarding the sensor measurements are described in ref. 3.

At the beginning of each experiment, the video camera was mounted above the visualization fixture. The flow patterns from the experiments were recorded with the high resolution video tape recorder. The video tape was used to determine the infiltration times and to provide a means of correlating the measured flow patterns with the predictions of the resin infiltration model. Fourteen images were captured from each taped sequence and stored in 32 bit form on a computer disk for later retrieval.

The fabric preform used in the visualization experiments was a style 162, plain weave, E-glass fabric. Eleven layers of the fabric were stacked into the fixture and compressed to the cavity thickness of 0.38 cm which gave a fiber volume fraction of 43%. The fluid used in the experiments was corn oil. A small amount of red dye was added to the oil. The viscosity of the oil and dye mixture was measured to be 40 cp.

The experimental set-up for the mold filling experiments consisted of a 0.36m x 0.36m picture frame mold. This size frame allowed for a 0.30m x 0.30m preform which was placed within the frame. A shim was then placed on top of the preform to ensure that the desired fiber volume fraction was achieved. A top plate with a venting port connected to a vacuum pump was then placed on top of the shim. The positive displacement injection pump was connected to the mold by high temperature plastic tubing. Resin enters the cavity through two side ports and flows along a 0.64 cm channel around the perimeter of the preform. A diagram detailing the mold assembly is given in Fig. 3.

The entire mold assembly was then placed into a press and heated at 90 °C. Both the injection pump and plastic tubing were heated at 90 °C. After a vacuum had been pulled on the mold to remove entrapped air, the injection was started with a constant flow rate. Injection was continued until a steady stream of resin could be seen in the exit hose connected to the vacuum trap.

Frequency dependent electromagnetic sensors were placed in the bottom of the mold to monitor the flow front position as a function of time during the injection process. Six sensors were used to monitor the infiltration patterns, with three located on the perimeter of the preform and three located in the interior of the preform. A schematic diagram detailing the sensor locations is given in Fig. 3.

The preform used in these experiments consisted of 16 plies of IM7/8HS compacted to a nominal fiber volume fraction of 60%. Shell 1895/Curing Agent W, mixed in a 3:1 ratio, was injected at a constant flow rate of 10 cc/min. The nominal viscosity of the mixed resin at 90 °C was 120 cp.

RESULTS

A schematic diagram of the single side port injection experiment was shown in Fig. 2. Resin enters the cavity through a single side port and flows along the 0.32 cm channel around the perimeter of the fabric. Resin then begins to infiltrate through the edges of the preform, saturates the preform, and exits through the center port.

The finite element mesh for the resin infiltration model consisted of 2707 quad elements and a total of 2816 nodes. The measured E-glass fabric warp and fill direction permeabilities at 43% fiber volume fraction were input for each element [4].

The influence of the channel was considered in the model by adjusting the permeability of the elements representing the channel until the model-predicted inlet port and channel pressures matched the measured values. This technique gave a reasonably good representation of the resin channel in the simulation.

Comparisons between the model-predicted and recorded flow fronts are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The time that the image was captured on the video tape is denoted on each figure. The dark shaded area is the resin saturated region of the preform, the whitish area is the dry preform and the solid line represents the model-predicted flow front. The images of the model-predicted flow fronts were taken at times corresponding to the images stored to disk from the video tape. Each model-predicted flow pattern was overlaid on top of the appropriate video image taken from the experiments.

As can be seen from the figures the model matched the measured infiltration times very well. Note that the measured flow front is somewhat wavy during infiltration. This may be due to the waviness of the plastic top plate.

A grid showing the positions of the FDEMS sensors, which are located underneath the glass fabric, has been overlaid on Figs. 4 and 5. The grid was helpful in comparing the FDEMS sensor response to the flow front position. The sensor locations and measured wet-out times are denoted on each figure. As can be seen from the figures, the FDEMS sensors can detect the location of the resin flow front to within 5s of the measured infiltration time. The accuracy of the FDEMS measurements can be improved by increasing the scanning rate of the data acquisition system.

The mold filling experiment was conducted with Shell 1895/W resin and IM7/8HS carbon preform at a flow rate of 10 cc/min. The purpose of the experiment was to use the FDEMS technology to monitor resin position as a function of time during the filling process and compare the recorded times with the model predicted values.

The finite element mesh for the resin infiltration model consisted of 620 quad elements and a total of 669 nodes. The measured IM7/8HS fabric warp and fill direction permeabilities at 60% fiber volume fraction were input for each element [4].

The resin flow patterns during mold filling are shown in Fig. 6. The locations of the six FDEMS sensors and the corresponding wet-out times are denoted on the figure. The wet-out of sensor #1 was used to approximate the beginning of the mold filling process. There is excellent agreement between the measured wet-out times and model predictions for both the internal (sensors #2, #3, and #5) and perimeter (sensors #4 and #6) sensor locations. Note the skewed flow pattern due to the shifting of the preform during mold closing. By carefully measuring the channel dimensions upon completion of the test, a more accurate prediction of the flow patterns at the beginning of infiltration was obtained.

A comparison between the measured and model-predicted mold inlet pressure is shown in Fig. 7. Pressure readings were also taken in the channel adjacent to sensor #4 and in the identical location

on the other side of the mold. The data indicate that the pressure drop in the channel is quite small, as expected. The model accurately predicts the pressure behavior as a function of infiltration time. The fluctuations in the pressure predictions are a result of variations in the injection pump flow rates.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A science based multi-dimensional RTM process simulation model has been developed which can describe the infiltration of resin into a dry textile preform, and cure of the resin saturated preform. The model can be utilized in the development of optimal cure cycles and in mold design by specifying the location of resin injection ports which result in complete wet-out of a complex shaped preform.

Frequency dependent electromagnetic sensing (FDEMS) has been developed for in-situ monitoring of the RTM process. The sensors are capable of monitoring resin-flow-front position during infiltration along with the change in resin properties during the cure cycle.

A series of flow visualization experiments was performed to obtain data which can be used to verify the sensor and the model. The results of these tests showed that FDEMS can accurately detect the location of the flow front in the mold during infiltration, and that the model-predicted flow front patterns agree well with the recorded flow front patterns.

The results of the mold filling experiments indicated that the RTM simulation model can accurately predict the resin flow patterns, infiltration times and inlet pressures. The mold filling experiments also showed that the FDEMS system can provide an indication of the resin flow patterns during the actual infiltration of the preform.

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Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the flow visualization apparatus.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of single side port injection experiment (left) and location of the FDMS sensors array in the visualization fixture (right).

Figure 3. Sketch of RTM mold assembly (left) and location of FDMS sensor array in bottom plate of RTM mold (right).

Figure 4. Comparison between the model-predicted and recorded flow front at an infiltration time of 20s.

Figure 5. Comparison between the model-predicted and recorded flow front at an infiltration time of 45s.

Figure 6. Model predicted flow patterns during mold filling for a flow rate of 10 cc/min.

Figure 7. Comparison between measured and model predicted inlet pressure for a flow rate of 10 cc/min.